

Satisfaction to the Front Liner Student Services: A Basis for the Service Improvement of Student Affairs and Services

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Abstract

Student affairs and services play an essential role in the holistic development of students within an academic institution. The overall educational experience and well-being of each student are influenced by the quality of services offered by the various units operating under the Office of Student Affairs and Services (OSAS). Thus, this study aimed to assess the satisfaction levels of Bataan Peninsula State University students regarding the services provided by the frontline offices supervised by the OSAS. To evaluate the performance of each office, the study employed a descriptive research design utilizing survey questionnaires. The findings revealed that the majority of services provided by the frontline offices were satisfactorily implemented, particularly those offered by the Scholarship office. However, certain aspects contributed to students' dissatisfaction, including the inefficiency and lack of organization in enrolment procedures, insufficient ventilation, chairs, and tables in the canteen, and the absence of a drinking fountain and dressing room within the campus. Furthermore, despite the university's regular evaluation of various units, it is imperative to consider but disseminate the results to the respective units to ensure that they are informed about their performance and encourages them to develop improvement plans in response to identified areas of concern.

Keywords: students affairs, frontline services, student satisfaction

Introduction

The Bataan Peninsula State University–Student Affairs and Services is committed to student-centered education which involves in providing quality support and development services to assists students to achieve their potential in their academic endeavors and succeed in their chosen career. Essential to the attainment of this goal is the assessment and evaluation of the performances of student services provided by frontline service offices for the continuous improvement of Student Affairs and Services unit. Since the quality of student support services has a strong influence on student retention, student’s learning and positive experiences within the University (Mahan 2001), it is necessary then that student services programs must be properly responsive to the needs of the students and the challenges of fast changing socio-economic and technological condition of our society.

Student services in higher educational institutions refer to the divisions that provide services, programs, and resources that help students learn and grow outside of the classroom (NASA, 2012). Generally, the services include enhancing student learning, providing guide academic and career decisions, mentoring students, promoting leadership skills, counselling students through crises and others. Frontline services in higher education institutions, on the other hand, refer to services directly provided to the students that may involve direct contact with them; these are admission services, registrar/record services, finance services, library, maintenance services, security services, guidance services, health services, and food services.

In compliance with the requirement of Policies and Guidelines on Student Affairs and Services (CMO N0. 9, s. 2013) by the CHED, every semester, the Office of the Student Affairs and Services of each campus of BPSU is tasked to undertake an evaluation of these services provided by the following offices: Registrar’s Office, Guidance Office, Cashier’s Office, Library, Clinic, School Cafeteria, Security, and Maintenance Services Unit. Most of these frontline services are under the supervision of the Office of Student Affairs and Services (OSAS) as indicated in its mandate. This segment of the University (OSAS) is commissioned to provide services and programs that are concerned with academic support experiences of students in attaining holistic student development. Academic support services are those that relate to student welfare, student development and those that relate to institutional program and services (CMO No. 09 s2013). As such, it supervises the following units or services: admission, guidance, health clinic, and school cafeteria.

Evaluating the performance of the frontline services by the students is very useful for the institutions to help responsible units identify their strengths and pinpoint areas that could be improved thereby providing excellent services to the most important client of the University, the students. The regular evaluation of the OSAS to the said offices serves as an instrument to measure the efficacy and assess their performance in order to know their strong and weak points in the delivery of their services. Results and findings provide feedback to the

staff regarding their performance thereby help them to make progress as they perform their specific job.

Hence, this research work intended to examine the satisfaction of the students to the services provided by frontline units as reflected in the evaluation of student services conducted by the OSAS, as well as to scrutinize the items in the evaluation tool to pinpoint the strength and weaknesses of delivery of services by each unit. Findings of this work can be used as basis for the Office of the Student Affairs and Services to designed more responsive programs of concerned units under its supervision and provide recommendation to other concerned units for improvement and better delivery of services.

Methods

The study used the descriptive research design to assessed the level of satisfaction of the students in Bataan Peninsula State University Balanga Campus to the Front Liner Student Services provided by OSA Practitioners during the Academic Years 2015-2018. The study utilized a convenient sample particularly the quota sampling. Participants were selected based on their availability during the scheduled conduct of survey by the researcher. On quota sampling, the researcher picked 360 students which are divided equally based on college and year level. Available personnel of frontline servicing units were also interviewed to elicit further information, clarification, and suggestions to contextualize the findings in the data analysis and discussion. Since, this research utilized previous data (Evaluation of Student Services 2015 – 2018) from OSAS, it is then worth to mention that participants during the time these evaluations were conducted and these were students currently enrolled during the time period and were also selected using convenient sampling. In determining the level of satisfaction, frequency count and weighted mean was utilized. To discriminate items along each of the services, the mean of each item was also supported by percentile rank to describe the strength of each item and the standard deviation to describe the homogeneity or heterogeneity of the responses. the Kruskal Wallis and the Mann Whitney U Test were utilized to determine the significant difference of the level of satisfaction along the Frontline Student Services and personal profile.

Results

There are ten units of the student services considered in this study namely: registrar, guidance, admission, scholarship, library, cashier, clinic, school cafeteria, security, and maintenance. Table 1 reflects the level of satisfaction of each unit based on how well it conducts and implement their duties, responsibilities, and programs.

Table 1. The Level of Satisfaction to the Frontline Service

Summary of the level of satisfaction to the frontline service from 1st semester of 2015 to 2nd semester of 2018

	2015-2016		2016-2017		2017-2018		MEAN	SD
	1st Sem SY 2015-16	2nd Sem SY 2015-16	1st Sem SY 2016-17	2nd Sem SY 2016-17	1st Sem SY 2017-18	2nd Sem SY 2017-18		
Student Services								
Registrar's Office	2.49	2.64	2.85	2.74	2.78	2.79	2.715	0.130
Guidance Office	2.14	2.31	3.09	3.01	3.02	3.21	2.797	0.452
Admission Office	2.66	2.78	2.95	2.87	2.99	2.98	2.872	0.130
Scholarship Office	2.65	2.78	3.12	3.16	3.18	3.25	3.023	0.246
Library	2.79	2.81	2.88	2.76	2.97	3.12	2.888	0.136
Cashier's Office	2.77	2.80	2.99	2.77	2.88	2.91	2.853	0.089
Clinic	2.68	2.51	3.03	2.98	3.04	3.08	2.887	0.234
School Cafeteria	2.45	2.63	2.57	2.55	2.70	2.63	2.588	0.086
Security	2.55	2.70	2.67	2.53	2.91	2.81	2.695	0.147
Maintenance	2.25	2.40	2.26	2.38	2.73	2.36	2.397	0.175
Gen Average	2.543	2.636	2.841	2.775	2.920	2.914	2.772	0.153

Interpretation: 3.25-4.00 = Strongly Agree; 2.50-3.24 = Agree; 1.75-2.49 = Disagree; 1.00-1.74 = Strongly Agree

Registrar Office

For the period SY 2015- 2016 to SY 2017-2018, the registrar was able to maintain its level of performance which is “satisfactory” in providing to the students with minimal improvement or an increase of 12%. With an average mean 2.79 or ‘satisfactory’, respondents demonstrate satisfaction with the services provided by the unit particularly in terms of information dissemination and informing students regarding their deficiency. However, they are least satisfied with the order and efficiency of enrolment procedures.

Guidance Office

There is a significant improvement in the performance of the Guidance office from 2.14 (fairly satisfied) in the 1st semester of SY 2015-2016 to 3.21 (satisfied) in the 2nd semester of 2017-2018. This entails a 50% development in the delivery of services of the Guidance as one of the OSA frontline services. The respondents are generally satisfied with the performance of the Guidance office, with an average mean of 3.21 interpreted as satisfied. The respondents expressed higher satisfaction on items involving the skills of the guidance counselor in

accommodating and assisting students in their guidance-related needs. Respondents are least satisfied in terms of giving feedback on personality tests and career guidance counseling.

Admission Office

There is a minimal improvement in the performance of the Admission Office though remained in a satisfactory level, from an average mean of 2.66 to 2.98. With an average mean of 2.98 interpreted as satisfied, the respondents express satisfaction with the services of the admission office, especially about the accessibility of the results of exams. However, respondents are least satisfied with the items related to assistance in career planning during the admission process.

Scholarship Office

The improvement in the performance of the Scholarship office ranges from the average mean of 2.65 (satisfied) to 3.25 (very satisfied). The improvement is attributed to the substantial increase of several scholarship programs offered by the University. With an average mean of 3.25 interpreted as very satisfied, respondents express higher satisfaction with the services of the Scholarship office. Particularly, respondents are very satisfied with the various scholarships offered by the University and the monitoring of the welfare of the scholarship grantees. The respondents are least satisfied compared to other items in the Dissemination of information such as posting on bulletin boards, brochures, and leaflets.

Library

The improvement in the performance of the Library is rated “fairly satisfied” with an average mean of 2.49 to “satisfied” with an average mean of 3.12. This registered a 25.3% increase. The respondents are generally satisfied with the services of the Library as it registered a rating of 3.12 with a descriptive rating of “satisfied”. Respondents express higher satisfaction on items related to the physical facilities of the Library such as adequate ventilation and furniture. On the other hand, they are least satisfied with the characteristics of library staff.

Cashier Office

There is a sustained average level of performance of the cashier within 3 years with an average mean of 2.8 with a descriptive rating of “Satisfied.” No noticeable improvement within the 3-year covered period. With an average mean of 2.91, the respondents demonstrate an average satisfaction with the services of the Cashier's office. The item that ranked first is the convenient location of the Cahier's office with a mean of 3.16, while the lowest in rank is the item relating to staff's courteousness and accommodation.

Clinic

There is a slight increase in the performance of the Clinic within the three-year covered period, from a mean of 2.68 to 3.08 which are both in the descriptive rating "Satisfied". The respondent's level of satisfaction with the service provided by the Clinic is descriptively rated as "satisfied" with a mean of 3.08. The item in which respondents were most satisfied was "clinic staff can provide emergency clinic" with a mean of 3.22 descriptively, while the item they were least satisfied with was "As a student I undergo medical check-up as the need arises" with a mean of 2.84. Both items are descriptively rated as "satisfied".

School Cafeteria

There is an almost stationary performance of the school cafeteria, from a mean of 2.45 to a mean of 2.63 both descriptively rated as "satisfied". No noticeable improvement was registered within the three covered years. The respondents have an average level of satisfaction with the services of the school cafeteria with a mean of 2.63. Respondents were highly satisfied with regards to the neat and courteous food handler with a mean of 2.86 descriptively rated as "satisfied", while they expressed least satisfaction in the items related to physical facilities like inadequate ventilation, chairs, and tables which are rated as "fairly satisfied".

Security

There is a slight improvement in the performance of security services as its average satisfactory rating within three years progressed from a mean of 2.55 to 2.81. The rating however did not move out of its rating satisfied. The respondents expressed an average level of satisfaction through a mean of 2.81 descriptively rated as "satisfied". Respondents were most satisfied with the item "I feel safe at BPSU" with a mean of 3.11, while expressed lowest satisfaction in item "All students receive equal treatment from the guard" with a mean of 2.48 descriptively rated as "fairly satisfied"

Maintenance

There is a sustained "fairly satisfied performance" of the Maintenance with a mean of 2.40 for three years, though it was able to reach a satisfactory rating with a mean of 2.73 during the 1st semester of SY 2017-2018. With a mean of 2.36, the respondents were fairly satisfied to the services of the Maintenance. Respondents were most satisfied with the items "Waste cans are located in accessible places on campus" and "Cleanliness of the School Areas" with a mean of 2.72 and 2.64 respectively. On the other hand, they were least satisfied with the items on the availability of drinking fountain and faucets and dressing room for PE and sports purposes, with a mean of 1.74 and 1.96, both with descriptive ratings "fairly satisfied". expressed higher satisfaction while the fourth-year respondents manifested higher level of satisfaction compared to other real levels.

Table 2. Summary of the Difference in the Level of Satisfaction to Frontline Services

	Colleges	Year Level	Age	Academic Performance	Sex	Civil Status
Registrar	1	1	0	0	0	0
Guidance	1	0	0	0	0	0
Admission	1	0	0	0	1	0
Scholarship	0	0	0	0	0	0
Library	1	0	1	0	1	0
Cashier	0	1	0	0	1	0
Clinic	1	0	0	0	0	0
Cafeteria	0	1	1	0	0	0
Security	0	0	0	0	0	0
Maintenance	1	0	0	0	0	0

Interpretation: 1 = Significant; 0 = Not Significant

The study examined satisfaction levels among respondents in various student affairs services, analyzing different profile variables. The Registrar's office revealed significant differences in satisfaction based on college and year level. Respondents of the College of Education (CoEd) and fourth-year respondents exhibited higher satisfaction. In Guidance services, only the College variable showed a significant difference, with CoEd respondents expressing higher satisfaction. Admission services displayed significant differences based on College and Sex, with CoEd and male respondents reporting higher satisfaction. Scholarship and Security services showed no significant differences. The library services exhibited significant differences based on college, age, and sex, with CoEd, '25 and above' age group, and male respondents reporting higher satisfaction. Cashiering service had significant differences in year level and sex, with third-year and male respondents expressing higher satisfaction. The Clinic displayed a significant difference based on the college variable, with CoEd expressing higher satisfaction. School cafeteria services showed significant differences in year level and age, with first-year and '25 and above' age groups reporting higher satisfaction. Maintenance services exhibited a significant difference based on the college variable, with CoEd respondents expressing higher satisfaction.

Discussion

The rating of the registrar's services showed that respondents are generally satisfied with the services provided by the registrar. Among the services provided that showed very good performance is the prompt dissemination of information especially regarding students' deficiencies and other important information. However, it is noteworthy to mention that there is a need to address the inefficient enrolment process as items on enrolment procedures consistently obtained the lowest rank. According to the registrar during the interview, perception of the inefficiency and disorganized enrolment procedures can be attributed first to the leniency of students in following the enrolment procedures like the "first come first serve" and "one transaction one student" rules; second, to the late encoding of grades by the instructors causing the tendency of students to revisit the registrar office multiple times.

The figure shows that there is a remarkable improvement in the performance of the Guidance Office with a six-semester period as it grew from 2.14 to 3.21 or a fifty percent increase, and nearly reaching a "very satisfied" rating. The progress of its ratings illustrates that the office was consistent in its intent to improve its services to the students. According to the guidance counselor, this was also the result of the regular conduct of orientation and seminars to the students. Students' negative perception or the stigma related to the guidance office has changed as they become more aware of its true functions and goals. Moreover, respondents were almost very satisfied with the performance of the guidance office particularly in their dealings with the guidance counselor. The "very satisfied rating" of the guidance counselor in terms of accommodating students and giving them advice illustrates the counselor's people skills such as good communicator and a good listener. On the other hand, the lower rank obtained by items on the interpretation of personality tests and having felt relieved after counseling sessions might be caused by a lesser number of students availing these types of services. It was possible that the majority of the respondents did not visit the guidance to take a personality test or for guidance counseling. Furthermore, some students who took personality tests did not take time to visit again the office to know the results of their tests according to the guidance counselor. Among the colleges, it was the COED that showed higher satisfaction compared to others. This higher level of satisfaction can be attributed to a higher number of education students availing guidance services and participation in other services like orientation, seminars, and training.

The figure on scholarship services shows a significant improvement in the services provided by the scholarship office as the rating upgraded from satisfactory to very satisfactory. This could be explained by the substantial increase in the number of scholarship programs offered by the University within the covered period. This has led to an increase in number of students availing scholarship form private and public organization through effort of the office. The higher rating given to the office by the respondents was also expected since this is the services that provide direct and tangible benefit to the beneficiaries of scholarship programs, according to the interview with student affairs personnel. In particular, the

University grants full and partial scholarship to those students who excel in their academics. Scholarship was granted also to members of arts and cultural groups such as the theater group and different dance group. Varsity players, student leaders and the staff of student publications were also granted institutional scholarship. Moreover, numerous scholarship both from public and private organization were being enjoyed by substantial number of students. Though still in the level of satisfaction rating, dissemination of information regarding scholarship, however must be given consideration as it got the lowest rank among the items.

The respondents were generally satisfied with the performance of the admission office but showed higher satisfaction on the accessibility of test results through tarpaulin and online website. The accessibility of information from the internet such as admission results proved to be a good practice as more and more people today rely on internet for easy and fast transactions.

The figure on the library services shows that was very little improvement in the services provided by the library throughout the 3-year covered period but the presence of declining performance in the midperiod (2nd semester of SY 2016-2017). This implies that either no significant change has occurred in the library within a covered period or any effort in improving the services has not been recognized by the students. However, the findings imply that the library provides a conducive physical environment for studying as items with adequate ventilation and library furniture that contribute to comfortable library work gained the highest rank among other items. Furthermore, the perception that library staff are strict, unapproachable, and unfriendly, according to the librarian, could be attributed to reminding and reprimanding students exhibiting boisterous behavior inside the library. Among the three colleges, respondents from the CoEd were more satisfied with the services provided by the library and this could be attributed to the number of CoEd students visiting the library. According to library staff, most students who visit the library come from the College of Education. Furthermore, they usually tend to have partnerships with CoEd student organizations in the implementation of their activities for promotion and other strategic activities.

The findings on cashiering services imply that the Cashier is on the right strategic and conspicuous location which can be easily accessed by the students, moreover, the waiting area with enough available seats for students waiting for their turn could also be attributed to the satisfaction of the students. On the other hand, respondents showed less satisfaction with regards to staff's conduct specifically of giving prompt service, and of being courteous and accommodating. This is confirmed by some comments from students stating that some cashier staff are not welcoming. Among the personal variables, only age and sex have a significant difference about the respondents' level of satisfaction, with "third-year" and "male" respondents showing higher satisfaction compared to other levels and females respectively. This implies these groups demonstrate patience and understanding in spite of waiting for

many hours due to long queuing. Further, cashier staff attested that they seldom encounter problems in their dealings with male students compared to female.

The findings on the services of the clinic imply that the staff have been very responsive to the immediate and emergency needs of the students. This also indicates that clinic personnel particularly nurses as well as emergency medicines and equipment are always available at any time. This could be justified also by the correct/proper schedule being set up by the nurses. The Office of Student Affairs always makes certain that clinic hours extend up to the last scheduled class of the day from Monday to Saturday. On the other hand, items that obtained lower satisfaction levels ("I undergo medical and dental check as the need arises) would imply that some students would tend to tolerate their medical and dental problems either because they are not aware of the free services provided by the clinic or they thought that will not be attended anyway due to unavailability of medical personnel. The latter however is understandable and expected as explained by clinic staff since both the dentist and doctor are also assigned at other campuses, hence would only be available for one or two days per campus. Among the personal variables, only the college variable has a significant difference in the satisfaction of the respondents with the services of the clinic. And it is the respondents from CoEd that expressed a higher level of satisfaction. This could mean that CoEd students are more aware of the services provided by the clinic and thus more of them are availing the said services. This claim was also attested by the nurses. They also stated that since CoEd students conduct more student extracurricular activities that require them medical certificates, naturally clinic visitors mostly come from the said college.

The figure on the school cafeteria indicates minimal improvement in the performance of the school cafeteria which would imply that no significant effort was extended to improve the quality of services provided by the canteen. It has been observed also by the respondents that the quality of service, the food being served, and the physical condition have not changed for several years. The findings imply that food handlers have been following the criteria in preparing and serving food as such as safety and sanitary conditions and the quality of food choices. It is expected however that safety and sanitary conditions are being satisfied by the canteen since the Office of Student Affairs requires the canteen a semi-annual sanitary permit from the Municipal Health Office as well as a health certificate from the food handlers. Moreover, the Clinic through the assigned doctor regularly checks the quality of food being served in the canteen.

Item referring to physical facilities and conditions of the canteen both obtained fairly satisfied rating, the lowest among all the items, this implies that students were not comfortable with the canteen's physical environment. Not only inadequate chairs and tables were the problem but also the lighting, ventilation and its location as it is situated at the far corner and darker side of the campus. The canteen staff however reasoned out that they cannot do something about the location and the inadequacy of equipment as they only depend on Administration's decision on where to place them inside the campus.

The figures on security services imply that the unit was able to maintain its performance on a satisfactory level but no significant improvement in its services has been observed. Based on interviews, there has been no modification in the way security personnel conducted their duties. However, the findings imply that respondents are generally satisfied with the services of the security unit except in an item referring to equal treatment of the guards to the students which implies that the guards might have been inconsistent in the implementation of rules and regulations and might have been playing favorites as also attested by the comments of some respondents.

The figures on maintenance services indicate that there is a slight improvement in the unit. Though the rating moved from fairly satisfied to satisfied in three covered periods, the movement was very minimal as it registered a 4.9% increase only. This implies that maintenance personnel conduct their activities the usual way and that no innovative ways of promoting cleanliness inside within the vicinity of the campus were introduced. The findings indicate that respondents were generally satisfied with the way the maintenance personnel performed their duties in upholding and preserving the cleanliness of the campus. However, they demonstrated little contentment about essential physical facilities that could attend to their needs such as comfort rooms, dressing rooms, and drinking fountains. This would mean that part of the problems encountered by students on campus is how to address their basic needs such as a clean comfort room and potable water to drink.

Among the personal variables, only the college variable has a significant difference, and it is the respondents from the COED that expressed higher satisfaction to the services provided by the maintenance. It has been observed by maintenance personnel that COED buildings and classrooms are generally cleaner compared to other colleges. This could be attributed, according to the head of maintenance, to the initiative and effort of COED particularly the student leaders through their projects and activities that uphold and preserve the cleanliness of the classrooms.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the findings and analyses of the study, it was found that:

1. Most of the services provided by the frontline units in BPSU Balanga Campus were satisfactorily implemented as eight out of the ten units garnered "satisfactory" rating from the respondents of the study. Scholarship is exemplary performing among the frontline servicing units since most of its indicators were rated "very satisfactory". Maintenance unit, on the other hand, was rated "fairly satisfied" in terms of its delivery of services.
2. Considering the entirety of the services provided by all the units, the items in which the respondents showed higher satisfaction are: the on-time and wide dissemination of information on academic records of the students and admission exam results; the

availability of numerous scholarship opportunities in the University; the skills and very welcoming attitude of the guidance counselor; the conducive venue for learning and study work in the library; the accessibility of the Cashier office; the prompt response of the Clinic on the emergency needs of the students; and the accommodating and kind behavior of canteen personnel.

The items that contributed to the dissatisfaction of the respondents, on the other hand, are: the inefficiency and lack of order of enrolment procedures; the seemingly no welcoming attitude of the library and cashier staff; the unequal treatment of the security personnel among the students; the inadequate ventilation, chairs and tables in the canteen; and the lack of drinking fountain and dressing room within the campus.

3. COED students were found to be more significantly satisfied in the services of the frontline servicing units than those from CBA and CSBS. This could be attributed to their active participation to the activities such as orientation and seminars given by the guidance office, clinic and library; and at the same time, they tend to avail more the services offered by these units. Hence, the extend of attendance and participation to the programs and activities provided frontline servicing units contributes to students' satisfaction to their services.

Male respondents were generally highly satisfied than their female counterpart in relation to the services provided by the Admission Office, Cahier Office and the Library. They were however satisfied similarly with the services of the rest of the frontline servicing units.

4. There is only incremental improvement in the delivery of services of almost frontline servicing units except the guidance office which progressed from the rating of "satisfactory" to "very satisfactory". Generally, all the units were able to perform at "satisfactory" level within the three-year covered period.

Upon a thorough consideration on the findings and conclusions derived from this study, the following recommendations were drawn as follows:

1. It would be worthwhile for all units of frontline services to consider the results of the semi-annual frontline services evaluation conducted by the Office of the Student Affairs and Services to analyze determine the effectiveness and efficiency of their service delivery and reflect on what they can do more to deliver quality services to the students.
2. Training on stress management and trainings that cultivate soft and people skills such as communication and listening skills, self-control, and positive attitude must be provided to the personnel of frontline offices. Being in the frontline service, they are expected to provide quality and positive experience to the clientele.
3. Frontline servicing units particularly the guidance office, clinic and library should develop plan such as extensive orientation and information dissemination on how to increase awareness, active participation and availment of services of students from the CBA and CSBS.
4. It is recommended that the frontline servicing units should be evaluated individually and not collectively. This is to ensure that each unit will be evaluated thoroughly by

covering all the areas/aspects of the unit concerned. To achieve this purpose, there is need to revise the present instrument since the items in the survey questionnaire per unit concerned are insufficient to generate more extensive and valid evaluations. Further, by evaluating all the units individually rather than collectively comparison between units would be sidestepped, consequently, the concerned can focus on its deficiency rather being more busied in comparing its performance with other units.

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